

Technical Report

Peer-to-Peer Platform for Corona-related Workforce

EOSCsecretariat.eu has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Programme call H2020-INFRAEOSC-05-2018-2019, grant Agreement number 831644.

Prof. Dr. med. Peter Langkafel MBA

Director School of Digital Health

e p.langkafel@xu-university.de

w xu-university.com

XU Exponential University

of Applied Sciences GmbH

Postanschrift: August-Bebel Straße 26-53 | 14482
Potsdam | Germany

Besucheranschrift: Lilian-Harvey-Straße I 14482 Potsdam

HRB Nr. 31080 P, UST-ID Nummer DE304974477

Content

Introduction..... 3

Why peer to peer?..... 3

Mathefragen.de as basis for the concept 4

Adoption to „FragenzuCorona“ 4

Customizing and Adoption of the Platform..... 5

 Step 1 Analyzing best practices 5

 Step 2 Define potential function and features..... 6

Communication 8

Evaluation..... 9

Introduction

The XU Exponential University near Berlin is Germany's first university that focuses exclusively on digitization and technology. At Studio Five on the premises of Studio Babelsberg in Potsdam, we have created a place that focuses specifically on the training, promotion, and networking of future experts of digital change.¹

The XU School of Digital Health was granted by the EOSCsecretariat.eu. We have received funding from the European Union's Horizon Programme call H2020-INFRAEOSC-05-2018-2019, grant Agreement number 831644.

Target of the program was to develop a prototype for a Peer-to-Peer Platform for Corona-related Workforce.

In the current Covid 19 pandemic, the rapid exchange of valid information (problem / question, solution options, evaluation) was and is essential. In order to offer fast digital support here, an "out of questions, experiences and error learning system" was urgently required.

Why peer to peer?

Peer education is an approach to health promotion, in which community members are supported to promote health-enhancing² change among their peers. Peer education is the teaching or sharing of health information, values, and behavior in educating others who may share similar social backgrounds or life experiences³

Peer-to-peer learning and exchange⁴ is essential for a structured exchange of information within the professions / institutions involved in health care and civil protection. Building and establishing a new solution takes too much time and ties up resources unnecessarily.

¹¹ <https://xu-university.com/en/about-xu/>

² Sriranganathan, G.; Jaworsky, D.; Larkin, J.; Flicker, S.; Campbell, L.; Flynn, S.; Janssen, J.; Erlich, L. (2010). "Peer sexual health education: Interventions for effective program evaluation". *Health Education Journal*. 71 (1): 62–71. doi:10.1177/0017896910386266. S2CID 72983724.

³ Boyle, J.; Mattern, C. O.; Lassiter, J. W.; Ritzler, M. S. (2011). "Peer 2 peer: Efficacy of a course-based peer education intervention to increase physical activity among college students". *Journal of American College Health*. 59 (6): 519–529. doi:10.1080/07448481.2010.523854. PMID 21660807. S2CID 39923580.

⁴ Green, J (2001). "Peer education". *Promotion and Education*. 8 (2): 65–68. doi:10.1177/102538230100800203. PMID 11475039. S2CID 45132844

The German Coalition for Patient Safety (APS)⁵ – in German "Aktionsbündnis Patientensicherheit (APS)", was established in 2005 and located in Bonn is a German non-profit association of organisations and individuals interested and involved in promotion of patient safety will support the piloting, growth and evaluation of the project.

APS' multidisciplinary working groups develop recommendations for patient safety activities in in- and outpatient healthcare institutions. The recommendations are available as open-access documents and distributed in healthcare institutions for free.

APS collaborates with professional and consumer associations, with societies, insurance organizations, self-governmental bodies, and research institutions. The Federal Ministry of Health is one of the organization's sponsors

Mathefragen.de as basis for the concept

Times of crisis need an unconventional approach: After an intensive research of the options it becomes clear that Mathefragen.de - Germany's best known and most popular mathematics exchange platform - can be quickly adapted, operated, and developed further. Crowd intelligence is used for optimization in the corona crisis.

Screenshot „Mathefragen.de“

Adoption to „FragenzuCorona“

⁵ <https://www.aps-ev.de/recommendations-in-english/>

Together with the team from mathefragen.de (Daniel Jung) a first design of the platform was created and adopted. This prototype was the basis to understand the customizing and adoption needs of the users

Customizing and Adoption of the Platform

In order to evaluate best practices of peer to peer platforms we analyzed some of the best in class platforms (non-healthcare specific, worldwide)

Step 1 Analyzing best practices

Agreement number 831644."								
Plattform	Domain	Beschreibung	Bewertung trusted.d	Estimated Number of Users / Questions	since when	sector / focus	business model	Country
Stack Overflow	https://stackoverflow.com/	Stack Overflow is an open community for anyone that codes. We help you get answers to your toughest coding questions, share knowledge with your coworkers in private, and find your next dream job.	2.1 von 5	10.000.000	2008	Coding	Charging money for posting jobs on their job exchange	USA
Mathefrage.de	https://mathefragen.de/	A tool for learning and helping to bring them together for learning in the best possible way. The portal is constantly being further developed and features are added to optimize the learning process. In addition, the goal is to evaluate learning data regarding when, how and with which method is asked and helped in order to individualize the learning process.	Keine Bewertung	18.000	2018	Math	Charging money for posting jobs on their job exchange	DE
GitHub	https://github.com/	GitHub provides code hosting services that allow developers/people to build software for open source and private projects in organizations. It designs and develops an online platform to allows users to store and share codes repositories with friends, co-workers, classmates, and complete strangers.	4 von 5	40.000.000	2008	Coding / Hosting	Subscription fees	USA
PatientsLikeMe	https://www.patientslikeme.com/	PatientsLikeMe, the world's largest personalized health network, helps people find new options for treatments, connect with others, and take action to improve their outcomes. The company has worked with every major pharmaceutical company and a range of government organizations to bring the patient voice to research, development and public policy. With more than 600,000 members, PatientsLikeMe is a trusted source for real-world disease information and a clinically robust resource that has published more than 100 research studies.	Keine Bewertung	600.000	2004	Health	Selling customer data to pharmaceutical companies	USA
Sermo	https://www.sermo.com/about/	The most popular site for healthcare providers on the web today, Sermo is focused on connecting "verified and credentialled" physicians from around the world in 150 countries, with plans to expand even further globally. Doctors can ask their peers anonymous questions regarding patient care in this "virtual doctors lounge". Currently the site has over 800,000 users.	Keine Bewertung	800.000	2005	Health	Healthcare institutions, financial services firms and government agencies purchase SERMO products to access this elite group of practitioners.	USA
Figure1	https://www.figure1.com/	This resource allows healthcare providers from around the world to share anonymous images of an ailment, such as x-rays, and compare them to other images available on the site. This tool is particularly useful for doctors in remote locations who may be treating a patient with a rare disorder. With millions of healthcare providers participating, it's become one of the largest digital platforms for medical professionals and an invaluable tool for saving lives.	Keine Bewertung	1.000.000	2012	Health - "Like Instagram for doctors"	Sponsored content and polls	USA
Daily Rounds	https://www.dailyrounds.org/	Available on desktop, Android and iOS, DailyRounds is a community of international physicians that's around 30,000 strong. The platform allows physicians to engage in chat, share medical expertise, load case files and access a drug database. It's a one stop network for physicians looking for professional advice and camaraderie.	Keine Bewertung	30.000	2013	Health	Offer medical apps for special cases	India

Based on this approach, we collected and defined detailed functions and features which where the basis for the further elaboration of the platform.⁶

Step 2 Define potential function and features

⁶ The full document is available at Zenodo Community

Feature	Description
General community features	
Set community access	Ability to make the community accessible only to logged in visitors or all visitors
Flexible community structure	Ability for moderators to define the community structure by creating and arranging categories and category groups
Basic community functionality	Visitors can vote / like and respond to topics
Private messages	Ability for users to send a private message to another user or moderator
Subscription / messaging / mailings	Ability to subscribe to a topic or category in order to receive updates on new replies
Live search	Increase the chance of finding the right content / answer by suggesting content when using the search functionality
Spam filter	
Basic spam detection	Ability to filter spam based on community sentiment/vocabulary
Advanced spam detection	Availability of self learning spam detection based on machine learning and natural language processing
Deployment model	
Deployment model	Platform is deployed in the cloud and provided as a service and automatically scales up on peak traffic
Data security	
Comply with key standards	ISO / EN / DIN
Regular audits	Company is audited yearly on the performance and reliability of the Information Security Management System by an external and objective IIOC member inspection firm
Questions and answers	
Create questions and answers	Users can create questions and answer these
Organize questions	Ability for a user to link a question to a category
Notification	Ability to receive email notifications on new questions or replies
FAQ creation	Ability to create FAQs based on popularity of a question
Discussion forum	(same as Q&A)
Registration and authentication	
Register and login	Ability to register and login from within the community application or using SSO
Moderation workflow / curation	
Flexible view of topics	The moderator tool has a default view that shows all topics and can select from this: all unanswered topics, all reported, all new etc
Content analysis	
Analyse posts and other content	Ability to report on sentiment analysis and content insights for the benefit of other departments like Marketing, Product Development, Customer Service, etc.
Reporting	Ability to provide stakeholders data reports based on tagged/annotated community content
Reports and analytics	
Key stats and trends	Availability to display a visual analytics dashboard in the community management tool, with charts and trend lines, on key statistics and trends: topics, comments, views, users, activity
In-depth reporting	Detailed reporting, eg on answered / unanswered questions
Integrate with 3rd party reporting	Ability to integrate Google Analytics as an external analytics tool to get an end-to-end view of community impact
"Gamification"	
Create ranks and roles	Ability for a moderator to create/manage a rank / role through an administration console - without programming
Automatic ranking	Ability to automatically give a user a rank / role / badge based on community activity
Organic search optimization	
Ensure high ranking in Google	Highly effective community ranking and content recognition, interpretation and adaptation by Google. Integrate with Google Search Console / Google Webmaster Tools for optimal web crawling results and data analysis. Support Open Graph metadata for community pages to provide automated crawling context to Facebook, LinkedIn, Google and Microsoft
Optimize pages for search	Optimized header and page structure semantics within community templates for optimal page crawling and ranking results

Communication

We presented our concept to several experts in the medical field. One major event of our project was the participation at one of the biggest hackathons – the WirVsVirus Hackathon with more than 42968 participants.

Screenshot Hackathon 1

Even so our project was not selected as one of the finalists (mainly because it was / is very much focused on professionals and less on general citizens) we had very in-depth feedback based on this event.

Screenshot Hackathon 2

Evaluation

To evaluate our concept, we had a fruitful discussion with several key opinion leaders of the topic, including the German network health literacy⁷

The German Network Health Competence eV (DNGK) is an interdisciplinary, non-profit association. The network develops, evaluates, and disseminates methods and concepts for promoting health literacy-

One of the targets of the organization is:

- promotion of initial, further, and advanced training through the development, implementation and support of teaching programs
- scientific-critical review and further development of methods to strengthen health literacy,
- Working with other groups active in the field of health literacy.

Additionally, we spoke to the president of the DEGAM, Prof. Dr. med. Martin Scherer (President. DEGAM is the German College of General Practitioners and Family Physicians,

“The Discipline of General Practice concerns the provision of basic health care to all patients with physical and mental health problems in the form of emergency, acute and long-term care. It also plays an important role in the areas of prevention and rehabilitation. As the first port of call, general practitioners specialize in helping patients with all kinds of health problems.”

We had the chance to present our concept to the Berlin Ministry of Health as well. Even we received very positive feedback from several experts there, the BGM was mainly focused on “firefighting” against the Covid-19 pandemic solution and could not stimulate a long-term funding based on and for German healthcare institutions. The main expectation and “wish” of all interviewed persons were to have a sustainable solution in the p2p space in healthcare.

⁷ <https://dngk.de/>